

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Development and validation of q-absorbance ratio method for simultaneous quantification of linagliptin and metformin HCl in synthetic mixture and combined tablets

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Abstract

The present study aims to develop and validate simple, cost effective Q-Absorbance Ratio Method for simultaneous quantification of Linagliptin (LIN) and Metformin HCl (MET). The proposed medium Acetonitrile: Methanol: Distilled Water at 1:1:1 (Solvent Blend) identified λ_{max} 235nm for MET, 298nm for LIN and Isobestic point at 231.7nm for Q-Absorbance Ratio Method. The validation follows ICH Q2(R1) guidelines, demonstrating excellent linearity, accuracy, precision and sensitivity (LOD and LOQ) for LIN and MET. The developed method was successfully applied to a synthetic mixture and marketed formulation, showing % recovery within the acceptable limit with % RSD was less than 2.

Keywords: Linagliptin; Metformin HCl; Q-Absorbance Ratio Method; Validation; ICH

1. Introduction

Linagliptin (LIN)^{1,2} appeared as white to pale coloured amorphous powder has melting point of 202°C, slightly soluble in DMSO, methanol and acetonitrile. Chemically LIN (figure 1) is 8-[(3R)-3 amino piperidin-1-yl]-7-(but-2-yn-1-yl)-3-methyl-1-[(4 methyl quinazolin-2-yl) methyl]-3, 7-dihydro-1H-purine 2, 6-dione. It is a Type 2 antidiabetic drug which acts by blocking the action of DPP-4, an enzyme that destroys the hormone GLP-1, which helps the body to provide more insulin when it is needed. It stimulates the release of insulin and inhibits the release of glucagon, resulting in the decrease levels of circulating glucose.

Metformin HCl (MET)^{3,4} is a white to off-white crystalline powder, has melting point of 226 °C, soluble in water, methanol, acetonitrile and varied buffer pH, insoluble DMSO. Chemically MET (figure 1) is 1-carbamimidamido-N, N-dimethyl methanimidamide hydrochloride. MET is a biguanide antihyperglycemic agent and first-line pharmacotherapy used in the management of type II diabetes, which decreases blood glucose levels by decreasing hepatic glucose production, decreasing the intestinal absorption of glucose, and increasing insulin sensitivity by increasing peripheral glucose uptake and utilization. It is well established that MET inhibits mitochondrial complex I activity, and it has since been generally postulated that its potent antidiabetic effects occur through this mechanism.

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Figure 1 Chemical structure of a) LIN and b) MET

The literature shown various methods for the estimation of LIN⁵⁻¹¹ and MET¹²⁻¹⁷ alone and in combination viz., UV¹⁸, HPLC^{19,20}, HPTLC^{21,22}, RP-HPLC²³⁻³⁷, LCMS³⁸. These methods require sophisticated instrumentation, expensive solvents, and complex sample preparation. Moreover, the use of organic solvents in chromatographic techniques raises environmental concerns due to solvent waste and associated health hazards.

To address these challenges, conventional UV spectrophotometric methods, including the Q-Absorbance Ratio Method (QARM)³⁹⁻⁴³ and the Simultaneous Equation Method (Vierordt's method), were selected for this study. These techniques offer a straightforward, cost-effective alternative to chromatographic methods, making them particularly suitable for laboratories with limited resources. Unlike chromatographic procedures, UV spectrophotometric methods do not require costly columns, organic solvents, or extensive sample preparation. Additionally, they provide a rapid and efficient means of quantification, especially for compounds with overlapping absorption spectra.

The QARM or Q-Absorption or Q-analysis method is one UV spectrophotometric technique used for the simultaneous quantification of two components in a mixture without prior separation. This method is based on the ratio of absorbances (Q-values) at two selected wavelengths viz., λ_1 (isoabsorptive point) where the wavelength at which both components have the same absorptivity and λ_2 is the λ_{max} (absorption maxima) of one of the components. By measuring the absorbances at these two wavelengths, the concentrations of both components can be calculated using the absorptivity coefficients^{44,45}. So far, Q- Absorption ratio spectrophotometric method was not reported for the estimation of LIN and MET in formulations.

Hence, the present research work was aimed to develop and validate Q-Absorbance Ratio UV spectrophotometric method for simultaneous quantification of LIN and MET in synthetic mixture and combined dosage forms.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

Drug sample of Linagliptin (LIN) and Metformin HCl (MET) were provided as a gift sample by Magnus Pharma Ltd, Nepal. Ondero Met 2.5/500 tablets, Trajenta Duo 2.5/500 tablets (Linagliptin/Metformin HCl) were purchased from local pharmacy store. Solvents like Acetonitrile, Methanol were purchased from SD Fine Chemicals, Mumbai. Distilled water was used throughout the study.

2.2. Apparatus

Instrument used was of Shimadzu UV-1900 series with a pair of 1cm path length matched quartz cells, software used was UV Probe. Anamed digital analytical balance was used for precise weighing. Validated glassware's were meticulously cleaned with distilled water and dried before use.

2.3. Preparation of standard stock solution

Stock solutions of LIN and MET were prepared separately by dissolving 25 mg of each drug in 25 mL solvent blend comprising Acetonitrile: Methanol: Distilled Water at 1:1:1 in a volumetric flask, resulting in a concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The solutions were sonicated for 10 mins to ensure complete dissolution. From each stock solution, 2.5 mL was withdrawn using a calibrated glass pipette and diluted to 25 mL with solvent blend to achieve a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for both LIN and MET.

3. Methodology

3.1. Determination of absorption maxima and wavelength selection

Stock solutions of LIN and MET were made appropriate dilution separately with solvent blend to obtain final concentrations of 10 µg/mL for LIN and MET. These solutions were scanned individually in the ultraviolet range (400 nm to 200 nm) and determine their maximum absorbance wavelength (λ_{max}). Overlay spectra of LIN and MET were generated and isoabsorptive point wavelength was selected.

3.2. Q-Absorbance Ratio Method (QARM)

The QARM which obeys Beer's law at all wavelengths, the ratio of absorbance at any single wavelengths is constant value independent of concentration or path length. At isobestic point nm solutions of both drugs of same concentration exhibit identical absorbance and consequently with zero difference. Such wavelengths of equal absorptivity of the two species are called isobestic or isoabsorptive points. QARM uses ratio of absorbance at two selected wavelengths, one which is an isoabsorptive point and other being the λ_{max} of one of two components. From overlay spectra of two drugs, it was evident that LIN and MET have an isoabsorptive point at 231.17 nm (λ_1). The second wavelength used was 235 nm of (λ_{max} of MET) or 298 nm of (λ_{max} of LIN). LIN and MET showed considerable absorbance at both wavelengths (figure 2). The concentration of two drugs of mixture in 1:1 ratio at 235 nm or 298 nm can be calculated using following equation,

$$C_x = \frac{Q_M - Q_Y}{Q_X - Q_Y} * \frac{A_1}{ax_1} \quad C_y = \frac{Q_M - Q_X}{Q_Y - Q_X} * \frac{A_2}{ay_1}$$

Where, A1 and A2 are absorbance of mixture solution at 231.7 nm and 235 nm

ax_1 = A (Absorptivity, 1 %, 1 cm) of LIN at 231.7 nm

ay_1 = A (Absorptivity, 1 %, 1 cm) of MET at 231.7 nm

ax_2 = A (Absorptivity, 1 %, 1 cm) of LIN at 235 nm

ay_2 = A (Absorptivity, 1 %, 1 cm) of MET at 235 nm

C_x and C_y are the unknown concentration of LIN and MET respectively in sample solution.

$Q_M = A_2/A_1$, $Q_X = ax_2/ax_1$ and $Q_Y = ay_2/ay_1$

3.3. Determination of linearity curve

Stock solutions of LIN and MET were made appropriate dilution with solvent blend in a series of sets of 10 ml volumetric flask to obtain 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 µg/mL solutions separately for LIN and MET. The absorbance of both solutions was taken at their respective λ_{max} viz., 298 nm for LIN and 235 nm for MET and at isoabsorptive point 231.7 nm. The linearity curves were constructed by plotting concentration against absorbance where each reading was an average of six determinations.

3.4. Preparation of test solution for assay

LIN (2.5 mg to 5 mg) and MET (500 mg to 2000 mg) alone and in combination LIN: MET in the ratio of 1:200 were used in the treatment of diabetes. Practicability of such ration make difficult for analytical estimation, to make simulation for the analytical study appropriate ratios of LIN: MET (2.5 mg: 12.5 mg; 2.5 mg: 25 mg) were chosen. Mix appropriately the stock solutions of LIN and MET to get simulated solutions viz., 1:5 and 1:10 and were considered as test solutions. Similarly sample test solution for marketed combined tablets were prepared. In each case 10 tablets were weighed and crushed into powder. The powder equivalent to 10 mg of LIN and 500 mg MET were extracted with solvent blend under the study for 2 hr, followed by sonication for 30 min. The content were filtered and the filtrate was collected and stored for further analysis.

4. Method validation

The proposed method was validated as per ICH guidelines Q2 (R1).

4.1. Precision

The precision of the proposed method was assessed as repeatability, intraday precision and interday precision. Repeatability was performed by applying six replicates of sample solution. For intermediate precision, Intraday and Interday precision was performed by determining corresponding responses of six replicates on same and different days for test solution containing LIN (10 µg/mL) and MET (10 µg/mL) alone and in mixture of LIN and MET. The results were reported in terms of % RSD.

4.2. Accuracy

Recovery studies were carried out by standard addition method. A known amount of standard LIN and MET viz., 50 %,100 % and150 % of the label claim were spiked to test solution of LIN (10 and 16 µg/mL) and MET (10 and 16 µg/mL). The results were reported in terms of % RSD.

4.3. LOD and LOQ

The LOD and LOQ of the developed method were calculated from the linearity curve using following equations,

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma/S; \quad \text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma/S.$$

Where,

σ = Standard deviation (y-intercepts of calibration curves) S= Slopes of linearity curves

5. Result and discussion

5.1. Absorption maxima and Isobestic point

The absorption maxima were found to be 235 nm, 298 nm respectively for MET and LIN and Isobestic point at 231.7 nm with characteristic peak as shown in figure 2.

5.2. Linearity

The linearity curve was constructed in the concentration range 2-10 µg/mL respectively for LIN and MET at their respective absorption maxima and at their Isobestic point nm, data was given table 1-3, linearity curves in figure 3 and overlay spectra in figure 4. The linear relationship between concentration and absorbance was studied by method of least square regression analysis, and relevant statistical and linearity curve data were given in table 4. The results suggest linear relationship with a correlation coefficient R^2 was 0.9899 to 0.9988 for LIN and MET.

Figure 2 Overlay absorption maxima spectra of LIN, MET and Isobestic point spectra in Solvent blend

Table 1 Linearity data of MET and LIN at 231.5 nm

MET at λ_1 n=6			LIN at λ_1 n=6		
Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance \pm SD	% RSD	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance \pm SD	% RSD
2	0.11 \pm 0.001528	1.384	2	0.305 \pm 0.00058	0.1891
4	0.22 \pm 0.001000	0.455	4	0.608 \pm 0.00058	0.0949
5	0.330 \pm 0.001732	0.525	6	0.911 \pm 0.00100	0.1098
8	0.440 \pm 0.000577	0.131	8	1.216 \pm 0.00153	0.1257
10	0.550 \pm 0.001528	0.277	10	1.519 \pm 0.00173	0.1140

Table 2 Linearity data of MET and LIN at 235 nm

MET at λ_2 n=6			LIN at λ_2 n=6		
Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance \pm SD	% RSD	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance \pm SD	% RSD
2	0.068 \pm 0.00153	0.742	2	0.084 \pm 0.00305	1.566
4	0.136 \pm 0.00057	0.325	4	0.165 \pm 0.00208	1.172
6	0.204 \pm 0.00057	0.219	6	0.242 \pm 0.00352	1.447
8	0.273 \pm 0.00153	0.434	8	0.324 \pm 0.00404	1.246
10	0.330 \pm 0.00153	0.346	10	0.404 \pm 0.00557	1.427

Table 3 Linearity data of MET and LIN at 298 nm

MET at λ_2 n=6			LIN at λ_2 n=6		
Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance \pm SD	% RSD	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance \pm SD	% RSD
2	0.090 \pm 0.00153	1.685	2	0.068 \pm 0.00200	0.941
4	0.176 \pm 0.01097	1.209	4	0.136 \pm 0.00115	0.844
6	0.271 \pm 0.0010	0.370	6	0.204 \pm 0.00116	0.565
8	0.284 \pm 0.00153	0.537	8	0.273 \pm 0.00159	0.565
10	0.358 \pm 0.00153	0.426	10	0.339 \pm 0.00100	0.295

Figure 3 Linearity curves a) MET at 231.7nm, b) LIN at 231.7 nm, c) MET at 235 nm, d) LIN at 235 nm e) MET at 298 nm f) LIN at 298 nm

Figure 4 Overlay Linearity spectra of a) LIN 2-12 µg/mL and b) MET 2-12 µg/mL

5.3. Precision

The Repeatability, Intraday and Interday precision data for test solution containing LIN 6 µg/mL and MET 10 µg/mL was given in table 4. The % RSD for repeatability was in the range of 0.5553 to 1.430, for Intraday precision 0.5075 to 1.326 and Interday precision 0.5453 to 1.332. The results suggest the adapted method was reproducible, reliable and precise for the simultaneous estimation of LIN and MET.

Table 4 Repeatability Intraday and Interday precision of MET and LIN

Precision	Concentration of test solution (µg/mL)	Absorbance ± SD n=6		% RSD	
		λ ₁ 231.7 nm	λ ₂ 235 nm	λ ₁ 231.7 nm	λ ₂ 235 nm
LIN					
Repeatability	6	0.9063±0.00503	0.2457±0.00351	0.5553	1.430
Intraday	6	0.9030±0.00458	0.2423±0.00321	0.5075	1.326
Interday	6	0.9047±0.00493	0.2413±0.00321	0.5453	1.332

MET					
Repeatability	10	0.5527±0.00550	0.3343±0.00451	0.9965	1.349
Intraday	10	0.5507±0.00153	0.3337±0.00416	0.5075	1.326
Interday	10	0.5463±0.00379	0.3317±0.00252	0.6930	0.7588

5.4. Accuracy

The accuracy data for LIN and MET form marketed sample solutions at three levels (50 %, 100 % and 150 %) of standard addition method was given in table 5. The % recovery for LIN was in the range of 99.00±0.577 (50 % level); 99.40±0.577 (100 % level); 99.26±0.171 (150 % level) with % RSD less than 2. The % recovery of MET was in the range of 99.40±0.231 (50 % level); 99.50±0.289 (100 % level); 99.33±0.156 (150 % level) with % RSD less than 2, the results suggest the method was accurate and can be used for assay and recovery study.

Table 5 Accuracy data of LIN and MET

Drug	Prequantified sample (µg)	% of pure drug added	Pure drug added (µg)	Amount Recovery µg/ml	Mean Recovery± SD	% RSD
LIN	10	50	5	4.95	99.00±0.577	0.5852
	10	100	10	9.94	99.40±0.577	0.5852
	10	150	15	14.89	99.26±0.171	0.1722
MET	10	50	5	4.97	99.40±0.231	0.2326
	10	100	10	9.95	99.50±0.289	0.2896
	10	150	15	14.90	99.33±0.156	0.1571

5.5. LOD & LOQ

The LOD and LOQ was calculated by standard formula as given in ICH guide lines and was given in table 6. The LOD was 0.0433 µg/mL and 0.1313 µg/ mL for LIN at λ₁ and λ₂; LOQ was 0.0521 µg/ mL and 0.3123 µg/ mL for LIN at λ₁ and λ₂. The LOD was 0.0512 µg/ mL and 0.1292 µg/ mL for MET at λ₁ and λ₂; LOQ was 0.0511 µg/ mL and 0.2143 µg/ mL for MET at λ₁ and λ₂.

5.6. Analysis of LIN and MET in test solution

The developed QARM was applied to sample mixture solution and marketed tablet solution and summary of the statistical and Q-absorbance data was given in table 6 and spectra of marketed sample solution was given in figure 5. The % Assay of LIN and MET synthetic mixture solution was 100.11±0.6311, 100.31±0.3345, 100.21±0.5811 and 100.43±0.1394 respectively of the labelled claim. The % Assay of LIN and MET marketed sample solution was 100.98±0.8721, 100.14±0.6689, 99.98±0.9213 and 99.78±0.8821 respectively of the labelled claim.

Figure 5 Spectra of test solution of LIN and MET

Table 6 Q absorption method and Validation parameters

MET		
Parameters	λ_1 (231.7)	λ_2 (235)
Specificity	Specific	Specific
Linearity Range	2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
Regression Equation	$Y = 0.05495*X + 0.000670$	$Y = 0.04400*X - 0.0004$
Molar Absorptivity	$ay_1 = 0.055 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$ay_2 = 0.043 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$
Absorbance of mixture	$A_1 = 0.9063 \pm 0.0050$	$A_2 = 0.2457 \pm 0.00351$
Analysis of mixture (LIN+MET)	100.11 ± 0.6311	100.31 ± 0.3345
Analysis of tablet (Mktd)	100.98 ± 0.8721	100.14 ± 0.6689
Sandell Sensitivity	$0.021 \mu\text{g/cm}^2$	$0.024 \mu\text{g/cm}^2$
Correlation Coefficient (R^2)	0.9986	0.9899
Repeatability (% RSD)	0.5553	1.430
Intraday (% RSD)	0.5075	1.326
Interday (% RSD)	0.5453	1.332
Accuracy % Recovery	99.23 ± 0.278	99.53 ± 0.193
LOD	$0.0512 \mu\text{g/mL}$	$0.1292 \mu\text{g/mL}$
LOQ	$0.0511 \mu\text{g/mL}$	$0.2143 \mu\text{g/mL}$
LIN		
Parameters	λ_1 (231.7)	λ_2 (235)
Specificity	Specific	Specific
Linearity Range	2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
Regression Equation	$Y = 0.1518*X + 0.001$	$Y = 0.03925*X + 0.0109$

Molar Absorptivity	$a_{x1} = 0.151 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$a_{x2} = 0.041 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$
Absorbance of mixture	$A1 = 0.5527 \pm 0.00550$	$A2 = 0.3343 \pm 0.00451$
Analysis of mixture (LIN+MET)	100.21 ± 0.5811	100.43 ± 0.1394
Analysis of tablet (Mktd)	99.98 ± 0.9213	99.78 ± 0.8821
Sandell Sensitivity	$0.027 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$	$0.023 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$
Correlation Coefficient (R^2)	0.9988	0.9980
Repeatability % RSD	0.5553	1.430
Intraday % RSD	0.5075	1.326
Interday % RSD	0.5453	1.332
Accuracy % Recovery	99.22 ± 0.5728	99.43 ± 0.1982
LOD	$0.0433 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	$0.1313 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$
LOQ	$0.0521 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	$0.3123 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$

6. Conclusion

For the simultaneous quantification of Linagliptin and Metformin HCl a new technique, such as Q-Absorbance ratio approaches, represent an enormous advancement in analytical chemistry. This approach is innovative because it uses extremely precise and repeatable UV spectrophotometric techniques. The proposed method concludes that Q-Absorbance Ratio Method can be successfully used for simultaneous estimation of Linagliptin and Metformin HCl both drugs in presence of each other.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Authors contribution

The collaborative efforts of all authors have successfully led to the development of a Q-Absorbance Ratio Method for simultaneous quantification of Linagliptin and Metformin HCl in commercially available combined tablets. Vasavi Yadav and Rishika Vaishnav, under the mentorship of N. Srinivasulu, conducted the development and validation of the technique. Y. Anand Kumar provided guidance in crafting the manuscript and structuring the research paper in accordance with the journal's guidelines.

References

- [1] Blech S, Ludwig-Schwellinger E, Grafe-Mody EU, Withopf B, Wagner K. The metabolism and disposition of the oral dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitor, Linagliptin, in humans. *Drug Metab Dispos* 2010; 38(4):667-678.
- [2] Graefe-Mody U, Retlich S, Friedrich C. Clinical pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of Linagliptin. *Clin Pharmacokinet* 2012;51(7):411-427.
- [3] Viollet B, Guigas B, Sanz Garcia N, Leclerc J. Cellular and molecular mechanisms of Metformin: an overview. *Clin Sci* 2012; 122(6):253-270.
- [4] Rena G, Hardie DG, Pearson ER: The mechanisms of action of Metformin. *Diabetologia* 2017; 60(9):1577-1585.

- [5] Smita SA, Saroj G, Ravindra B. Spectrophotometric and Chromatographic estimation of Linagliptin in bulk and tablet dosage form. *Int J Chem Tech Res* 2017; 10:736-744.
- [6] Sneha RB, Anvesha VG, Krishna RG. Quality by Design based HPLC assay method development and validation of Linagliptin in tablet dosage form. *EJPMR* 2017; 4:486-494.
- [7] Sara SM, Eman IE, Dalia AH, Magda AB. Stability indicating HPLC-DAD method for the determination of Linagliptin in tablet dosage form: Application to degradation kinetics. *J Chromatographic Sci* 2016; 54:1560-1566.
- [8] Sahloul L, Salami M. Development and validation of a new analytical method for determination of Linagliptin in bulk by Visible spectrophotometer. *Sci Rep* 2023; 11; 13(1):4083.
- [9] Srikanth Reddy K, Rajasekharan S. Method development and validation of Linagliptin by using RP-HPLC technique. *JETIR* 2025; 12(5): i558-i572.
- [10] Dalal A, Tegeli V, Waghmode R. Development and validation of a simple and rapid UV spectrophotometric method for Linagliptin in bulk and marketed dosage form. *Der Pharma Chem* 2022; 14(2):23-26.
- [11] Barapatre SR, Ganorkar AV, Gupta KR. Quality by design-based HPLC assay method development and validation of linagliptin in tablet dosage form. *Eur J Pharm Med Res* 2017; 4(02): 486-494.
- [12] Mohamed YA, Mohamed AM, Mohamed FA, Ahmed SA. New salting out stability indicating and kinetic thin layer chromatographic method for determination of Metformin HCl binary mixture. *J Chromat Sci* 2015; 53(9):1603-1610.
- [13] Vaingankar PN, Amin PD. Development and validation of stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for determination of Metformin HCl fixed-dose combination. *Anal Chem Insights* 2016; 11:13-20.
- [14] Vemula P, Dodda D, Balekari U, Panga S, Veeresham C. Determination of Metformin by RP-HPLC method. An application in quantitative analysis of pharmaceutical dosage forms *J Adv Pharm Tech Res* 2015; 6(1):25-28.
- [15] Gopal NM, Sridhar C. A validated stability indicating ultra-performance liquid chromatographic method for simultaneous determination of Metformin hydrochloride drug and tablet dosage form. *Int J Applied Pharm* 2017; 9(3):45-50.
- [16] Vankalapati KR, Alegete P, Boodida S. Stability-indicating ultra-performance liquid chromatography method development and validation for estimation of Metformin in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. *Biomed Chromat* 2021; 35(4):5019.
- [17] Sen AK, Hinsu DN, Sen DB, Zanwar AS, Maheshwari RA, Chandrakar VR. Analytical method development and validation for estimation of Metformin hydrochloride from its pharmaceutical dosage form by three different UV spectrophotometric methods. *J Appl Pharm Sci* 2016; 6(9): 157-165.
- [18] Konari SN, Jacob JT, Prakash V. Stability indicating UV spectrophotometric method for Linagliptin and Metformin in pharmaceutical dosage form. *Pharm Methods* 2017; 8(2): 121-126.
- [19] El-Bagary RI, Elkady EF, Ayoub BM. Spectrophotometric methods for the determination of Linagliptin in binary mixture with Metformin hydrochloride and simultaneous determination of Linagliptin and Metformin hydrochloride using High Performance Liquid Chromatography. *Int J Biomed Sci* 2013; 9(1): 41-47.
- [20] Afzal SJS, Asif M, Khan PMAA. Validation of stability indicating high performance liquid chromatographic method for simultaneous determination of assay of Linagliptin and Metformin drugs in the pharmaceuticals tablet formulations using Bupropion as a common internal standard. *Euro J Biomed* 2018; 5(2), 1111-1119.
- [21] Ragini AP, Chainesh NS. Method development and method validation of HPTLC for stability indicating and simultaneous estimation study of Linagliptin and Metformin in combination dosage form. *Pharma Sci Mon* 2017; 8(1):63-74.
- [22] Srivani J, Uma Mahesh B, Veeresham C. Development and validation of stability indicating HPTLC method for simultaneous determination of Linagliptin and Metformin. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci* 2016; 8(1), 112-115.
- [23] Chandrabatla V, Asif Md, Ramakrishna K. RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Metformin and Linagliptin in tablet dosage form. *Rasayan J Chem* 2015; 8(4):426-432.
- [24] Janardhan Swamy A, Harinadha Baba K. Analytical method development and method validation for the simultaneous estimation of Metformin HCl and Linagliptin in bulk and tablet dosage form by RP HPLC method. *Int J Pharm* 2013; 3:594-600.

- [25] Shirisha S, Akiful Haque M, Sireesha D, Vasudha B, Harshini S. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Metformin and Linagliptin in combined pharmaceutical dosage Form. *Int J Pharma Res Health Sci* 2014; 2(6):491-495.
- [26] Sheena M, Rohini Reddy G, Sunil Kumar CP, Priyanka G, Hima Bindu E. Simultaneous determination of Metformin Hydrochloride and Linagliptin by RP-HPLC in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. *Indo American J Pharma Res* 2014; 4(10):4047-4053.
- [27] Prasad PBN, Satyanaryana K, Krishnamohan G. Development and validation of a stability indicating method for simultaneous determination of Metformin Hydrochloride and Linagliptin in a formulation by RP-HPLC. *Int J Pharma Res Rev* 2016; 5(6):16-22.
- [28] Varun Kumar G, Pavan Kumar V, Gobinath M, Hari Baskar V, Ramesh D, Vijitha Y. Analytical method development and validation by RP-HPLC for the simultaneous estimation of Linagliptin and Metformin in bulk and combined tablet dosage form. *IJCTPR* 2015; 3:1110-1115.
- [29] Prasanna ACK, Pavani S, Priyanka K. Method development and validation of Linagliptin and Metformin by using RP-HPLC in pharmaceutical dosage form. *Int J Adv Pharma Sci* 2015; 6:2673-2678.
- [30] Prathyusha V, Dilip D, Umamahesh B, Shyam D, Ciddi V. Simultaneous determination of Linagliptin and Metformin by reverse phase-high performance liquid chromatography method: An application in quantitative analysis of pharmaceutical dosage forms. *J Adv Pharm Tech Res* 2015; 6(1):25-28.
- [31] Rutvik HP, Rajeshwari R, Dilip GM. Bioanalytical method development and validation for simultaneous determination of Linagliptin and Metformin drugs in human plasma by RP-HPLC method. *Pharmacophore* 2014; 5(2):202-218.
- [32] Kavitha KY, Geetha G, Hariprasad R, Kaviarasu M, Venkatnarayanan R. Development and validation of stability indicating RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Linagliptin and Metformin in pure and pharmaceutical dosage form. *J Chem Pharma Res* 2013; 5(1): 230-235.
- [33] Pandya RH, Rathod R, Maheshwari DG. Bioanalytical method development and validation for simultaneous determination of Linagliptin and Metformin drugs in human plasma by RP-HPLC Method. *Pharmacophore* 2014; 5(1): 202-218.
- [34] Vemulla P, Dodda D, Ballekari U, Panga S, Veeresham C. Simultaneous determination of Linagliptin and Metformin by reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography method: An application in quantitative analysis of pharmaceutical dosage forms. *J Adv Pharm Tech Res* 2015; 6(1): 25-28.
- [35] Varaprasad C, Asif M, Ramakrishna K. RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Metformin and Linagliptin in tablet dosage form. *Rasayan J Chem* 2015; 8(4): 426-432.
- [36] Khushbu P, Ujashkumar AS, Hirak VJ, Jayvadan KP, Chhaganbhai NP. QbD stressed development and validation of stability-indicating RP- HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Linagliptin and Metformin HCl in pharmaceutical dosage form. *Res J Pharm Tech* 2022; 15(5):1917-1923.
- [37] Reddy PE. RP-HPLC Method for simultaneous Estimation of Metformin and Linagliptin in Pharmaceutical formulation. *Asian J Biomed Pharm Sci* 2024; 14(103):214.
- [38] Moussa BA, Mahrouse MA, Fawzy MG. A validated LC-MS/MS method for simultaneous determination of Linagliptin and Metformin in spiked human plasma coupled with solid phase extraction: Application to a pharmacokinetic study in healthy volunteers. *J Pharma Biomed Ana* 2019; 163:153-161.
- [39] Ashok HA, Divya KS, Sagarkumar KP, Palak D, Gamit J, Bhavesh P et al. Development and validation of a novel simultaneous equation and Q-absorbance ratio method for the quantitative estimation of Atenolol and Hydrochlorothiazide in combined tablet dosage forms: A green analytical chemistry approach. *Green Anal Chem* 2025; 12:100224: ISSN 2772-5774.
- [40] Amitkumar JV, Brijesh HP, Ashok BP, Ajay IP, Nilesh KP. A brief review on Q-absorption Ratio Method in UV-Spectrophotometry. *Asian J Pharma Anal* 2022; 12(4):281-285.
- [41] Ruchi HM, Akruiti K, Vaibhav BP. Spectrophotometric method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of Anagliptin and Metformin HCl by Q - Absorption ratio method in synthetic mixture. *Heliyon* 2020; 6(5):e03855.

- [42] Jignesh P, Rajesh KP, Neha SM. Q-Absorbance Ratio spectrophotometric method for simultaneous estimation of Nimesulide and Diclofenac sodium in combined pharmaceutical dosage form. *Int J Res Manage Pharm* 2017; 6(3): ISSN: 2320- 0901.
- [43] Akshaykumar S, Vaibhav RV. A new analytical Q-Absorbance Ratio Method development and validation of UV spectrophotometric method for simultaneous estimation of Quercetin and Monoammonium Glycyrrhizinate in gel formulation. *IJCRT* 2020; 8(4):2134-2142.
- [44] Beckett AH and Stenlake JB. *Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry-Part Two*, CBS, New Delhi, India, 4th edition, 2005.
- [45] Hirt RC, King FT, Schmitt RG. Graphical absorbance-ratio method for rapid two-component spectrophotometric analysis. *Anal Chem* 1954; 26(8):1270-1273.